

SPECTROCHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF COPPER AND CADMIUM IN THE PRECIPITATES OF CADMIUM AND COPPER QUINALDINATES

By. A. K. MAJUMDAR

Following the method of Nitchie, quantitative spectral analyses of Cd and Cu, adsorbed in the precipitates of Cu and Cd respectively, have been made.

In previous communications (Majumdar, *Analyst*, 1939, 64, 874 ; 1943, 68, 242) it has been shown that copper can be separated from cadmium in presence of sulphuric acid by means of quinaldinic acid following the method of Rây and Bose (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1933, 95, 400).

Lindsay and Shenan (*Analyst*, 1940, 65, 636), who failed to obtain a satisfactory separation by this method, showed by means of cation that the copper precipitate always contained cadmium. Cadion, whose high sensitivity approaches one part of cadmium in 300 million parts, is, however, unsuitable for obtaining a quantitative estimate of the amount of cadmium in the copper precipitate.

With a view to obtaining a quantitative idea about the amount of cadmium and copper adsorbed in the precipitates of copper and cadmium respectively, the present spectro-analytical work was undertaken, in which the method of Nitchie (*Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1929, 1, 1) was followed for quantitative spectral analysis.

EXPERIMENTAL

The strength and the amounts of standard solutions, the procedure adopted for the precipitations, the manner of washings of the precipitates of copper and cadmium, were exactly the same as was reported in a previous paper (*Analyst*, 1943, 68, 242) except that the precipitates were filtered through Schleicher and Schull's white-band filter paper No. 590. The precipitates were then taken in separate crucibles, decomposed to anhydrous sulphates by heating with concentrated sulphuric acid (reagent quality) and transferred into the cavities of different electrodes of purified gas carbon.

Where, according to the earlier paper already mentioned, the quantity of copper taken for analysis was 26.7 mg., the entire sulphate of copper was put in the lower positive electrode. If, however, the copper taken was double this amount, the sulphate was then made up to 50 c.c. with double distilled water, 25 c.c. of which were evaporated to dryness and the residue used for spectral analysis.

Similar procedure was also adopted in the case of cadmium. If the quantity of cadmium were 30.95 mg., the entire sulphate was taken, but if it was double or treble this amount, the sulphate was made up to a definite volume with water and half or one-third of the total volume taken for use.

For the purpose of preparing a series of standard plates, representing different percentages of cadmium in copper (e.g. 0.1 to 0.01), the same quantity of standard

copper sulphate solutions containing 26.7 mg. of copper was taken in several crucibles. A definite amount of dilute standard cadmium sulphate solution of concentrations varying from 26.7×10^{-3} mg. to 26.7×10^{-4} mg. were added to each crucible along with 15 c.c. of 1% solution of quinaldinic acid. The solution in each crucible was then converted into anhydrous sulphate as mentioned above and the entire mass was used for arcing.

In the same way standard plates from 0.1 to 0.5% of copper in cadmium, were prepared by using 30.95 mg. of cadmium sulphate solution and varying amounts of copper (30.95×10^{-3} mg. to 15.485×10^{-2} mg.) from diluted standard copper sulphate solutions.

A large Littrow-type E_1 -quartz spectrograph was used and the spectrum from λ 2350 to λ 3400 Å, distributed over 10 inches, was photographed on Ilford Special Rapid plates. No special treatment of the plates has been found necessary.

The electrodes used were of carbon, 33 mm. long, 9 mm. in diameter and the positive rod contained a cavity 5 mm. wide and 4 mm. deep into which samples were introduced. The negatives were sharpened to fine points which helped in centering and steadying the arc.

The electrodes were purified according to the method of Staud and Ruehle (*Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1938, 10, 59) and prior to adding the sample, they were burnt for 30 seconds in 10.5 ampere arc to eliminate any remaining impurities.

A quartz condensing lens was used to concentrate the light from the arc on the slit. Suitable adjustments were made permitting the arc to be moved both horizontally and vertically, so as to keep it properly centred.

The tips of the electrodes were kept, as far as possible, at a constant distance from each other to maintain current and voltage drop constant, and the image of the arc properly centred on the slit aperture.

For each sample, a three-minute exposure was given with a current of 10.5 ± 0.5 amperes. The time was sufficient for the complete vaporisation of the samples.

R E S U L T S

Lines used for comparison in the case of cadmium arc were λ 3403.8 and λ 3261.2 Å.

TABLE I

Metals taken.	2N-H ₂ SO ₄ .	Reagent added (quinaldinic acid 1% neutralised by Na ₂ CO ₃)	Cd in Cu ppt.	Cu in Cd ppt.	Plate No. for Cd in Cu.	No. for Cu in Cd.
Cu, 26.7 mg. Cd, 30.95	2 c.c.	30 c.c.	0.06%	0.3%	24	27
Cu, 26.7 Cd, 61.9	5	30	0.07	0.3	39	30
Cu, 26.7 Cd, 92.85	2	30	0.06	0.3	31	32
Cu, 53.4 Cd, 30.95	10	60	0.05	0.3	38	34

Standard plates for cadmium in copper are Nos. 23, 25 and 37 containing respectively 0.1%, 0.07% and 0.04% of cadmium (Plate I).

In developing the plates, the concentration of the developer, the time for developing and fixing were maintained constant for every plate. It may be seen that the copper precipitate contains only 0.05 to 0.07% cadmium. On the other hand, the cadmium precipitate shows a comparatively large amount—about 0.3% of copper in it. In any case, the adsorption of cadmium in copper or of copper in cadmium is not likely to affect to any material extent the results of quantitative separation of copper from cadmium by the quinaldinic acid method, as already established in previous communications.

My best thanks are due to Prof. P. Rây and Dr. J. Gupta for their kind interest in the work.

INORGANIC CHEMISTRY LABORATORY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE,
CALCUTTA.

Received December 2, 1943.